

Transforming Banking Services: A Customer Oriented Approach

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Abstract

Financial sector reforms were initiated as part of overall economic reforms in the country and wide-ranging reforms covering industry, trade, taxation, external sector, banking and financial markets have been carried out since mid 1991. A decade of economic and financial sector reforms has strengthened the fundamentals of the Indian economy and transformed the operating environment for financial institutions and banks in the country.

Further, deregulation has opened up new opportunities for banks to increase revenues by diversifying into investment banking, insurance, credit cards, depository services, mortgage financing, securitisation, etc. At the same time, liberalization has brought greater competition among banks, both domestic and foreign, as well as competition from mutual funds, NBFCs, post office, etc. Increasing competition is squeezing profitability and forcing banks to work efficiently on shrinking spreads. Positive fallout of competition is the greater choice available to consumers, and the increased level of sophistication and technology in banks. As banks benchmark themselves against global standards, there has been a marked increase in disclosures and transparency in bank balance sheets as also greater focus on corporate governance.

In view of different issues pertaining to a theme, this paper focuses on the, conceptual reading of customer-oriented approach, outlook of banking in India, and key transformations in banking services. In this paper have studied private

and public banks of visnagar to find out how different banking services have transformed or how banks have become more innovative keeping in mind customers. Literature review and secondary data were also used for the study.

Introduction: A Customer Oriented Approach

Customer oriented approach is a set of strategies, processes, metrics, organizational culture and technology solutions that enhance an organization's ability to manage the differences in its customers' and prospects' behavior and needs, track new opportunities to better serve their customers and act, instantly and profitably, on those differences and opportunities. Recently it has taken a center stage in the business world with businesses concentrating on saving money and increasing profits by redefining internal processes and procedures. It costs a company dramatically less to retain and grow an existing client, than it does to court new ones. It is said that *"It is seven times more expensive to acquire a new customer than to keep an existing one"*, therefore the value of customer information and management should never be underestimated.

Customer relation management analysts say " Customers are King in real sense now". What's new is the technology is allowing us to do what we could do at the turn of the century with the neighborhood grocer. He had few enough customers and enough brainpower to keep track of everyone's preferences.

The advanced business environment and the technological changes have allowed us to go back to the future to this model." The aim of customer centric business model is optimize the use of technology and human resources for the business to gain insight into the need, preferences and behavior of costumer. Considering the

latest marketplace (COA) come out, the world's leading businessmen and industries have reinvented themselves to focus on customers, and there has been a violent rivalry for the supremacy in this market. Financial, manpower and technology related strengths are now essential for the customer oriented business approach, hence planning and allocation of resources before considering customer point of view business goals, is a recipe for disaster. Now, it is significant to keep in mind for managers that business policy used should be 'tailor made' depending on the type of consumer base of the company. Technology like call center services and software's will prove helpful only if they improve the customer services and relation, otherwise all fancy technology is useless if it fails to benefit the customer.

Objectives and Methodology of the Study

The main objective of the study was to find out how banks have incorporated customer oriented practices for different kind and category of consumers. To meet the defined objective a study was carried out through internet by accessing the web sites of various banks, referring books, journals, magazines, and other secondary data sources. In addition to this 3 private sector and 4 public sector banks of Visnagar (a city in North-Gujarat region) were visited to get the opinion of bank managers of all the banks about the customer centric practices in banking.

An Outlook - Banking in India

The Indian banking can be broadly categorized into nationalized (government owned), private banks and specialized banking institutions. The Reserve Bank of India act as a centralized body monitoring any discrepancies and shortcoming in the system. It is the foremost monitoring body in the Indian financial sector. The nationalized banks (i.e. government-owned banks) continue to dominate the Indian

banking arena. Industry estimates indicate that out of 274 commercial banks operating in India, 223 banks are in the public sector and 51 are in the private sector. The private sector bank grid also includes 24 foreign banks that have started their operations here. Under the ambit of the nationalized banks come the specialized banking institutions. These co-operatives, rural banks focus on areas of agriculture, rural development etc.,

Since the nationalization of banks in 1969, the public sector banks or the nationalized banks have acquired a place of prominence and has since then seen tremendous progress. The need to become highly customer focused has forced the slow-moving public sector banks to adopt a fast track approach. The unleashing of products and services through the net has galvanized players at all levels of the banking and financial institutions market grid to look anew at their existing portfolio offering. Conservative banking practices allowed Indian banks to be insulated partially from the Asian currency crisis. Indian banks are now quoting a higher valuation when compared to banks in other Asian countries (viz. Hong Kong, Singapore, Philippines etc.) that have major problems linked to huge Non Performing Assets (NPAs) and payment defaults. Co-operative banks are nimble footed in approach and armed with efficient branch networks focus primarily on the 'high revenue' niche retail segments.

The Indian banking has finally worked up to the competitive dynamics of the 'new' Indian market and is addressing the relevant issues to take on the multifarious challenges of globalization. Banks that employ IT solutions are perceived to be 'futuristic' and proactive players capable of meeting the multifarious requirements of the large customers base. Private banks have been fast on the uptake and are

reorienting their strategies using the internet as a medium. The Internet has emerged as the new and challenging frontier of marketing with the conventional physical world tenets being just as applicable like in any other marketing medium.

The Indian banking has come from a long way from being a sleepy business institution to a highly proactive and dynamic entity. This transformation has been largely brought about by the large dose of liberalization and economic reforms that allowed banks to explore new business opportunities rather than generating revenues from conventional streams (i.e. borrowing and lending). The banking in India is highly fragmented with 30 banking units contributing to almost 50% of deposits and 60% of advances. Indian nationalized banks (banks owned by the government) continue to be the major lenders in the economy due to their sheer size and penetrative networks which assures them high deposit mobilization.

We find current era of hyper competition, marketers are forced to be more concerned with customer retention and loyalty - this is all because of the key recommendations of the Narasimham Committee. The committee much stressed on two aspects one is banking efficiency and another is better customer service. It also indirectly advocated, as retaining customers is less expensive and perhaps a more sustainable competitive advantage than acquiring new ones. The consequence of such suggestions was the entry of the private and foreign players in the banking sector in India. The new private and foreign banks are more professional in their approach; customer centric, efficient operations with IT enabled services, with diverse range of service facilities etc.- they have been able to gain large customer base with the handsome amount of profits. This new banks have already captured the urban and semi-urban areas with their hi-tech,

sophisticated and professional way of working. Moreover, the personnel efficiency of such banks is a lot superior and enhanced that of the conventional public sector banks. The organized effort of managing the NPAs enabled them to bring it at the negligible level. Some of the top banks in India are Abn Amro Bank, Allahabad Bank, American Express Bank, Andhra Bank, Bank Of India, Canara Bank, Central Bank Of India, Citibank, Corporation Bank, HDFC Bank, HSBC Bank, ICICI Bank, Indian Overseas Bank, Oriental Bank Of Commerce, Punjab National Bank, State Bank Of India (SBI), Standard Chartered Bank, IDBI, United Bank Of India, and UTI bank.

Key Transformations in Banking Services

Globalization, liberalization and privatization have fueled the rapid transformations mainly through de-regulation and technological improvements of innovations in banking over the past quarter century. The introduction various modern terms and concepts emerged in the banking sector. Major transformations are found in the areas like banking hours, types of accounts, internet and mobile banking; IT enables services, loans and advances, credit and debit cards facilities etc.

24 Hour Banking

Banks are also attempting to reach out to residents of metropolitan cities where people are pressed for time (what with long commuting hours, traffic jams and both spouses working), beyond conventional banking hours. ICICI Bank, for example, introduced eight to eight banking hours, seven days of the week, in major cities. Some of the other private banks have also done this. HDFC Bank even has a 24-hour branch at Mumbai's international airport.

Saving Account

Some bank accounts combine a savings deposit account with a fixed deposit. A '*sweep-in account*', as it is called, works like this: the account will have a cut-off, say, Rs 25,000; any amount over and above that gets automatically transferred to a fixed deposit which will earn the customer a clean 2 per cent more than the returns that a savings account gives. Kotak Mahindra Bank had introduced a variant of the sweep-in account. If the balance tops Rs 1.5 lakh, the excess runs into Kotak's liquid mutual fund. Even if the money is there only for the weekend, a liquid fund can earn the customer a clean 4.5 percent per annum. And if, meanwhile, the customer want to buy a big-ticket home theatre system, the minute you swipe your card the invested sum will return to his account.

IDBI Bank has also tried to innovative its services by introducing the new schemes. Two years ago, for instance, it introduced instant account opening to its customers. The account holders are given account numbers, ATM cards and cheques books as soon as they filled in their account opening forms.

ICICI, UTI and many other banks have come out with a unique at par cheque facility. The salient feature of the facility is that the customer is needed to make DD, simply what he has to do is to write the cheque and the money can be with drawn from any of the branches treating it as a local cheques, this saves time of the customer as no cheque is treated as out station cheque. At the same time this saves customer's money which he has to pay in the form of bank commission.

ATMs

Several banks are bringing ATMs to customer doorsteps. ICICI Bank, State Bank of India and Bank of India now have mobile ATMs or vans that go along a

particular route in a city and are stationed at strategic locations for a few hours every day. This saves the bank infrastructure costs since it has one mobile ATM instead of multiple stationary ones.

That's not all. Even money is delivered to customers at home. Kotak Mahindra Bank, a late entrant into private banking, delivers cash at the doorstep. A customer can withdraw a minimum of Rs 5,000 and up to a maximum of Rs 2 lakh and get the money at home. Kotak is not alone. The list of banks offering a similar service includes Citibank, StanChart, ABN Amro and HDFC Bank.

Banks are innovating their services by establishing corporate relationship with many companies by providing them services at their doorstep. ICICI Bank set up the ATMs in a corporate headquarters (Infosys) to tap the company's salary accounts. Now many banks have established corporate relationship with many corporates.

Another innovation comes from IDBI Bank. This is "ATM Next" -- possibly the first service of its kind in the world. The bank is downloading information from the Internet and making it available to customers at the ATMs. This includes live cricket scores, news headlines, local movie listings and emergency contact numbers

Phone and Mobile Banking

HDFC Bank brings even foreign exchange, whether travelers cheques or cash, to your doorstep courtesy its tie-up with Travelex India. All one has to do is call up the branch or HDFC Bank's phone banking number. A StanChart customer can also access his account through the mobile phone by sending an SMS. ABN Amro uses

mobile phones to alert its customers on their credit card transactions. "Card Alerts", which come in the form of an SMS, are not necessarily a customer demand.

Mobile phones are playing an important role in Indian banking -- both directly and indirectly. They are increasingly being used both as a banking channel and for other services. Both IDBI Bank and HDFC Bank are offering instant mobile refill facilities through ATMs and SMS banking. This service has only just been launched in Europe and India is among the few countries in Asia to have it.

Internet Banking

Internet banking and shopping have been a slow starter, given the low computer penetration in the country but banks are going all out to get the customer online. HDFC's internet banking provides the customer options to make his credit card payment, download statements, change customer profile, transfer funds, open fixed deposit account, issue DD, make TDS inquiry, stop payment, make cheques status inquiry, make cheques book request. Not only these features but banks also offer other features that benefit the customer. HDFC Bank has an option called 'One View' on its Internet banking site, which provides customers a comprehensive view of their investments and fund movements. Customers can look at their accounts in six different banks on one screen. These include HDFC Bank accounts and de-mat accounts, ICICI Bank, Citibank, HSBC and Standard Chartered Bank accounts, apart from details of Citibank credit card dues and so on.

Credit Cards

Using credit card for online is no more a safe game now as credit card hacking has become common now a days. HDFC has come out with a unique credit card

scheme known as 'Net Safe'. HDFC Bank's 'Net Safe' card is a one-time use card with a limit that's specified, taken from customers credit or debit card. Even if customer fails to utilize the full amount within 24 hours of creating the card, the card simply dies and the unspent amount in the temporary card reverts to his original credit or debit card.

Home Loans

There some people who want to buy a house but don't want to go through the hassles of haggling with brokers and the mounds of paperwork? Not to worry about bank today tackle all this. It's ready to come every step of the way buying a house. Standard Chartered, for instance, has property advisors to guide a customer through the entire process of selecting and buying a house. They also lend a hand with the cumbersome documentation formalities and the registration. If the customer have already bought house or car. He can leverage his new house or car with banks like ICICI Bank and Stan chart are ready to extend loans against either, till it's about five years old. Loans are available to all car owners for almost all brands of cars manufactured in India that are up to five years old.

Banks have also come up with innovations in interest rates. ABN Amro sent the home mortgage market afire with its 6 per cent home loan offering. The product offers a 6 per cent interest rate for two years after which the interest rate is reset in tune with the prevailing market rate. All the other big home loan players slashed their rates after this was announced. Citibank, HSBC and Stan chart have brought out new variant in the home loans market with their unique home loans scheme. The balance one maintains in the savings account with the bank determines the interest rate on the loan. The homebuilder can maintain a higher balance in his or

her savings account and bring down the interest rate on the home loan. The rate is calculated on a daily basis on the net loan amount. Standard Chartered Bank has linked its customer's home loan account with a current account, where the principal amount of the loan gets reduced on a daily basis as the excess cash in the current account automatically flows in towards repaying the home loan.

IDBI has introduced 110 per cent home loans. The provocation for launching the product is the fact that for the first few years, most people live in a home devoid of the things that make it a home. IDBI Bank's home loan allows customers to buy their home and use the additional 10 per cent to furnish it and add amenities immediately.

Car loans

A car loan is another turf where competition is forcing innovation. Standard Chartered is offering loans of up to 75 per cent of the value of a car less than five years old. Even though it is classified as a personal loan, the rate is cheaper because the loan is secured against the car and the money can be used for anything. Normally, personal loans are costlier because they are unsecured loans

Specialized Products

State Bank of India is trying to go to the doorsteps of different professional groups in a unique way. State Bank of India has introduced a product called "Teacher Plus", where the teaching community is offered a bundle of products like home loans, car loans, personal loans and so on at a concessional rate. Similar products were subsequently introduced for lawyers, doctors and policemen. Now the bank is extending the segmented approach further to launch a package for the tourism industry covering travel agents, hoteliers and holidaymakers.

Citi Bank have come on the similar with its product known as "Junior Package", where the bank's specially trained investment counselors help parents to create wealth to meet the long-term needs of their children through regular investment schemes. It also allows the child to learn money management through India's first child ATM/debit card.

Adding other products with banking

HDFC Bank has pioneered other innovations. Take point of sale (POS) terminals, a prerequisite in any store or restaurant worth its name in the country. It tied up with Reliance Infocomm to offer mobile POS terminals. Although this are not in a trend today, there could soon be a day when people would these cards to pay their cabby, the pizza home delivery boy and even for the groceries from the local kirana store.

Banks are not only up with new products in banking but they are also attaching other products to banking. One such good example is of ABN Amro Bank's 'Bancafe'. The Dutch bank has tied up with the Barista chain of coffee shops to open its first Bancafe in Bangalore. Now, there are three others: two in Delhi and one in Kolkata. While the bank branch attached to the coffee shop opens at 1000 IST and closes at 1900 IST, the coffee shop is open from 0730 IST to 2300 IST. Here, a customer can walk in anytime and look at the interactive screen on insurance and mutual fund products and strike deals for car loans or personal loans for foreign travel even as he sips hot coffee with the travel agent sitting next to him.

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